

EFFECT OF WEED MANAGEMENT ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF SUMMER GROUNDNUT (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) UNDER SOUTH GUJARAT CONDITION

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted during the summer 2023 at Agricultural experimental Station, Paria, Gujarat with the objectives to determine the effect of different weed management treatment on growth and yield of summer groundnut under south Gujarat condition. The experiment designed in randomized block design with four replications. The treatments were T₁: unweeded control, T₂: weed-free hand weeding at 20, 30, and 40 DAS, T₃: pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (EC) at 1.0 kg/ha + 1 HW, T₄: pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (CS) at 1.0 kg/ha + 1 HW, T₅: pre-emergence application of flumioxazin (SC) @ 0.05 kg/ha + 1 HW, T₆: pre-emergence application of diclosulam (WDG) at 20 g/ha (PE) + 1 HW; T₇: pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (EC) at 1.0 kg/ha (PE) + imazamox + imazethapyr at 70 g/ha in pre-mix as post-emergence; T₈: post-emergence application of propaquizafop (EC) at 75 g/ha. The results revealed that significantly higher values of growth parameter viz., plant height, yield attributing parameters viz., number pods per plant, shelling percentage, test weight, harvest index and pod as well as haulm yield were recorded under weed free (Hand weeding at 20, 30 and 40 DAS) (T₂). Treatment T₃ and T₄ were found equally effective in recording higher values of growth parameters and yield attributes and yield than rest of treatments. The results of the study showed that T₂ (weed-free, hand-weeding at 20, 30, and 40 DAS) produced the best outcomes, whereas T₃ and T₄ herbicide treatments produced results that were comparable to T₁.

Key words: Groundnut, weed, pendimethalin, growth, yield.

Introduction

Groundnut is one of the most important oilseed crop in India and regarded as "king of oilseed crops". Groundnut products include peanut oil, flour, peanut butter and protein. Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is a leguminous oilseed crop native of South Africa belonging to the family Fabaceae and sub-family Papilionaceae (Hammons, 1982). Although it is grown in all continents, over 75 per cent of the total world groundnut production is concentrated only in India, China and the United State of America. In 2022, India contributed nearly 19% to global production of groundnuts. India ranks first in area and second in production after China. Groundnuts are grown on 6.09 million hectares of land in India, yielding 10.21 million tonnes at a productivity of 16.76 q/ha (Anon., 2023). In India, the states of Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Maharashtra account for 80% of groundnut area and 84% of production. Gujarat is the top producing state for groundnuts in India, contributing 35.50 percent of the total area (2.16 mha) and 40.42 percent of the total production (4.13 million tonnes), with an average productivity of 19.08 q/ha (Anon., 2023). Gujarat's Saurashtra area is known as the "Bowl of Groundnut."

Groundnut is an important food, fodder and cash crop for the farmers of India. Groundnut kernels contains 48-50 per cent of edible oil and 26-28 per cent protein, along with rich dietary fiber, minerals and vitamins (Ntare *et al.*, 2008). Weed infestation is the main biotic factor behind groundnut productivity being low, among other biotic and abiotic issues. Groundnut yields are significantly reduced because weeds fight with crop plants for nutrients and take away 30-40% of applied fertilizers (Dryden and Krishnamurthy, 1997). Groundnut production losses of up to 70% were noted as a result of weed infestation during the key period for crop-weed competition, which was found to be up to 45 days after sowing (Prasad *et al.*, 2002). Generally, weeds are controlled through hand weeding in groundnut, but it is expensive and laborious. However, to manage these weeds the availability of labours at the right time and at nominal cost is the biggest challenge being faced by the farmers. In such cases, chemical weed control may be a practical and affordable alternate method of managing weeds. An efficient herbicide used at the right dosage may prove to be an effective weed control strategy and take the place of more traditional weed control techniques. Due to the scarcity and high cost of labour, farmers have recently expressed a greater interest in using herbicides to manage weeds and lower cultivation costs (Savu *et al.*, 2005). Very scare scientific information is available particularly regarding weed management in summer groundnut grown under south Gujarat condition. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken

with the objective of finding suitability of different pre- and post-emergence herbicides.

Material and method

The field experiment was carried out during summer season of the year 2023 on Plot No. 2 of Agricultural Experimental Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Paria, Gujarat. Geographically the campus of Agricultural Experimental Station in Paria is located at 20°44' N latitude and 72°97' E longitude, at an altitude of 12 m above the mean sea level. The maximum and minimum temperature during crop growth period ranged between 26.07 to 39.04 °C and 10.36 to 25.00 °C, respectively during 2023. The soil of the experimental field was clayey in texture, slightly alkaline in reaction with pH (7.68) and EC (0.38 ds/m), low in available nitrogen (238.6 kg/ha), medium in organic carbon (0.52 %) and available phosphorus (50.8 kg/ha) and high in potassium (356.2 kg/ha). A combination of 8 treatments, viz. T₁: unweeded control, T₂: weed-free hand weeding at 20, 30, and 40 DAS, T₃: pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (EC) at 1.0 kg/ha + 1 HW, T₄: pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (CS) at 1.0 kg/ha + 1 HW, T₅: pre-emergence application of flumioxazin (SC) @ 0.05 kg/ha + 1 HW, T₆: pre-emergence application of diclosulam (WDG) at 20 g/ha (PE) + 1 HW; T₇: pre-emergence application of pendimethalin (EC) at 1.0 kg/ha (PE) + imazamox + imazethapyr at 70 g/ha in pre-mix as post-emergence; T₈: post-emergence application of propaquizafop (EC) at 75 g/ha, were tested in randomized block design. Pre- and post-emergence herbicides were applied manually using knapsack sprayer fitted with flat-fan nozzle by mixing in 500 litre of water/ha as per treatments. Groundnut cv. GG 34 was sown on 8th February, 2023 keeping spacing of 30 cm between row by using seed rate of 100 kg/ha. The recommended dose of fertilizers, i.e. 12.5 kg N/ha and 25 kg P₂O₅/ha was applied before sowing in the seed row zone. Nitrogen and P₂O₅ were applied through urea and DAP, respectively. The initial plant height and population were counted at 30 days after sowing. Whereas final plant height and population were counted at harvest. The crop was harvested on 26th May, 2023. The pod and haulm yield of groundnut was recorded at time of crop harvest separately for each net plot and converted into kg/ha. The harvest index was calculated by using formula suggested by Donald and Hamblin (1976) and registered against each treatment.

$$\text{Harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Economic Yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{Biological Yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)}}$$

The statistical analysis of the data of various characters studied in the investigation was carried out by using statistical procedure appropriate to the randomized block design as described by Panse and Sukhatme (1967), and the differences were tested by 'F' test.

Result and Discussion**Weed**

The weed flora of the experimental field was dominated by *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Sorghum halepense*, *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Barcharia Spp.*, *Amaranthus viridis*, *Digera arvensis*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Eclipta alba*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Cassia tora*, *Trianthema portulacastrum* and *Cyperus rotundus* during summer 2023.

Growth attributes

The results revealed that all the weed-control measures including weed-free control significantly improved the growth parameters, except plant population, over unweeded control (Table 1 and figure 1). The various weed management treatments did not exert any significant influence on plant population at 30 DAS and harvest, indicating no phytotoxic/ inhibitory effect of different herbicides on groundnut crop. Pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₃), pendimethalin CS @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₄), and pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + Imazamox + Imazethapyr @ 70 g/ha in pre-mix as post-emergence (T₇) had almost equal effect on plant height at 60 DAS and were at par with weed free (hand weeding at 20, 30, and 40 DAS) (T₂). At harvest, the higher plant height (48.93 cm) was noted with T₂ weed free – hand weeding at 20, 30, and 40 DAS, which remained statistically at par with pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₃), pendimethalin CS @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₄). While lower plant height (31.03 cm) at harvest was recorded under unweeded control (T₁) at harvest. It could be because of increased competition between weeds and crop plants as a result of poor weed management. A favourable environment for plant growth was created by the efficient control of weeds using hand weeding in treatment T₂ (weed-free) and a combination of pre-emergence herbicides and hand weeding, which reduced weed-crop competition throughout the crop's growth stage. Thus, improved access to nutrients, water, light, and space may have speed up the rate of photosynthetic energy production, which in turn increased the supply of carbohydrates and caused a rise in plant height. These findings are in agreement with those of Nambi *et al.* (2019), Bhattarai *et al.* (2021) and Kakade *et al.* (2023).

Yield and yield attributes

The yield attributes *viz.*, number pods per plant, shelling percentage, test weight, harvest index and pod as well as haulm yield were significantly influenced by weed management methods (Table 2 and figure 2). The treatment T₂ (weed free) produced the higher number of pods per plant (38.68) and remained at par with pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₃). While test weight (52.81 g) and shelling percentage (70.61 %) were recorded maximum in with treatment weed free (T₂) being at par with treatment pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₃) and pendimethalin CS @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₄) and pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + Imazamox + Imazethapyr @ 70 g/ha in pre-mix as post-emergence (T₇).

Pod yield (3625 kg ha⁻¹) and haulm yield (4940 kg ha⁻¹) were maximum in treatment T₂ (weed free) being at par with pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₃) and pendimethalin CS @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₄). The treatment weed free (T₂) recorded maximum harvest index (42.30 %) being at par with pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₃), pendimethalin CS @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW (T₄), pendimethalin EC @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + Imazamox + Imazethapyr @ 70 g/ha in pre-mix as post-emergence (T₇), flumioxazin SC @ 0.05 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW (T₅), diclosulam WDG @ 20 gm/ha (PE) + 1 HW (T₆). The successful weed control in the mentioned treatments enhanced the groundnut's growth and yield-contributing characteristics, resulting in a significantly higher pod yield compared to the unweeded control. These findings were in agreement with results Vora *et al.* (2019) and Kundu *et al.* (2021).

Conclusion

It can be concluded from study that potential production and effective weed control in summer groundnut can be achieved by keeping weed free (Hand weeding at 20, 30 and 40 DAS) conditions during the crop growth period. When labours are not easily available, apply either pendimethalin (EC) @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW at 40 DAS or pendimethalin (CS) @ 1.0 kg/ha as pre-emergence + 1 HW at 40 DAS.

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Table 1. Effect of different treatments on growth attributes of groundnut

Treatments		Plant population per net plot		Plant height (cm)		
		30 DAS	At Harvest	30 DAS	60 DAS	At harvest
T ₁	Unweeded Control	220.70	213.93	9.25	17.07	31.03
T ₂	Weed free (Hand weeding at 20, 30 and 40 DAS)	221.40	219.06	9.86	29.42	48.93
T ₃	Pendimethalin (EC) @ 1.0 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	220.06	216.26	9.72	27.51	46.58
T ₄	Pendimethalin (CS) @ 1.0 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	220.23	216.13	9.69	27.56	44.09
T ₅	Flumioxazin (SC) @ 0.05 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	219.40	215.26	9.49	23.07	37.46
T ₆	Diclosulam (WDG) @ 20 gm/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	219.20	214.06	9.41	21.80	36.45
T ₇	Pendimethalin (EC) @ 1.0 kg /ha (PE) + Imazamox + Imazethapyr@ 70 gm/ha (Pre-mix) as Post-Emergence	219.53	216.60	9.63	24.92	41.53
T ₈	Propaquizafop (EC) @ 75gm/ha as Post-Emergence	219.46	214.60	9.36	20.12	33.39
S.Em. ±		8.65	11.03	0.41	1.19	6.45
CD at 5%		NS	NS	NS	3.49	10.98

PE, Pre-emergence; HW, hand-weeding; DAS, days after sowing; EC, emulsifiable concentration; CS, capsule suspension; SC, soluble concentrate; WDG, water dispersible granule.

Table 2. Effect of different treatments on yield and yield attributes

Treatments		Number of pods/plants	Shelling percentage (%)	Test weight (g)	Pod yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Haulm yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
T ₁	Unweeded Control	20.43	60.57	38.67	1565	2730	36.34
T ₂	Weed free (Hand weeding at 20, 30 and 40 DAS)	38.68	70.61	52.81	3625	4940	42.30
T ₃	Pendimethalin (EC) @ 1.0 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	36.15	67.69	50.85	3258	4488	42.06
T ₄	Pendimethalin (CS) @ 1.0 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	35.71	67.02	50.73	3118	4361	41.65
T ₅	Flumioxazin (SC) @ 0.05 kg/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	26.18	65.54	46.89	2613	3964	39.78
T ₆	Diclosulam (WDG) @ 20 gm/ha (PE) + 1 HW at 40 DAS	25.18	65.03	45.45	2550	3905	39.50
T ₇	Pendimethalin (EC) @ 1.0 kg /ha (PE) + Imazamox + Imazethapyr@ 70 gm/ha (Pre-mix) as Post-Emergence	31.30	66.67	49.55	2918	4213	40.83
T ₈	Propaquizafop (EC) @ 75gm/ha as Post-Emergence	24.15	63.20	41.67	2212	3636	37.73
S.Em. ±		1.17	1.35	1.47	164.78	229.01	1.08
CD at 5%		3.44	3.98	4.32	484.62	673.53	3.17

PE, Pre-emergence; HW, hand-weeding; DAS, days after sowing; EC, emulsifiable concentration; CS, capsule suspension; SC, soluble concentrate; WDG, water dispersible granule.

Figure 1. Effect of different treatments on plant height

Figure 2. Effect of different treatments on pod and haulm yield